

Environment

- Server: Task execution failure (A01).
- Connection: Connection loss (A02).
- Web:
 - Connection loss in HTTP requests (A03).
 - Connection loss in HTTPS requests (A04).
- FTP: Task execution failure in transaction management (A05).
- SQL:
 - Failure in content access (A15).
 - Failure in permission granting (A06).
- Task Execution:
 - Failure in asynchronous task execution (A07).
 - Failure in asynchronous task execution (A08).
- Data: Data loss and failure (A09).
- Integrity:
 - Loss of data stored on servers (A10).
 - Failure in access control rules (A11).
- Durability: Failure in data durability state (A12).
- Availability:
 - Failure in data exposure (A13).
 - Failure in data access (A14).

Architecture

- Security:
 - Session management failure (Q01).
 - Input validation failure (Q02).
- Interface:
 - Authentication failure (Q03).
 - Authorization failure (Q04).
- User Authentication: Loss of authentication in restricted areas (Q05).
- Encryption: Cryptographic mechanism error (Q06).
- Digital Certificates: Digital certificate mechanism failure (Q07).
- Tokens: Security failure in token decoding (Q08).
- Data Availability:
 - Persistence: Security failure in offline persistence (Q09).

- Data Integrity: Data security failure (Q10).
- Efficiency:
 - Performance mechanism failure (Q11).
 - Access mechanism failure (Q12).
- Performance:
 - Resource contention failure (Q13).
 - Cache usage failures (Q14).
- Concurrent Access:
 - Data scalability failure (Q5).
 - Deadlock prevention failure (Q15).
 - Low performance in socket usage (Q16).
- Operational Performance:
 - Connection failure when viewing media (Q19).
 - Size: Data handling failure (Q20).
 - Table Size: Failure in materialized view mechanism (Q21).
 - Restricted Memory Usage: Slow operations with aligned vectors (Q22).
 - Cache Necessity: Cache mechanism failure (Q23).

Integration

- Legacy:
 - Documentation unavailability (I01)
 - Technological obsolescence (I02)
 - Complex dependencies (I03)
- Functionality Access: API compatibility failure (I04)
- Communication Methods: Low performance in microservices communication (I05)
- Data Exchange:
 - Data compliance failure (I06)
 - Real-time data exchange failure (I07)
- Third-Party:
 - Plugin integration failure (I08)
 - Notification cycle failures (I09)
 - Services: Failure with hotspots via third-party applications (I10)
 - Performance degradation (I11)
 - APIs: Loss of versioning configuration (I12)
 - Frameworks:
 - * Framework compatibility failure (I13)
 - * Framework versioning failures (I14)

- Hybrid Development:
 - * Compatibility failure (I15)
 - * Versioning failure (I16)
 - * Performance failure when using the framework (I17)
- Ionic:
 - * Compatibility failure with Ionic (I18)
 - * Versioning failure in Ionic (I19)
- Electron:
 - * Compatibility failure with Electron (I20)
 - * Versioning failure in Electron (I21)
- Security:
 - * Session authentication failure (I22)
 - * Session management failure (I23)
- JWT:
 - * JWT validation failure (I24)
 - * JWT signature failure (I25)
 - * JWT status verification mechanism failure (I26)
- Authentication:
 - * Authentication mechanism failure (I27)
 - * Failure in storing authentication credentials (I28)
- Configurations:
 - * Dependency failure (I29)
 - * Versioning configuration failure (I30)
- Libraries:
 - * Library configuration error (I31)
 - * Library dependency failure (I32)
- Requests:
 - * SOAP configuration loss (I33)
 - * Response validation failure (I34)
- Persistence:
 - * Error handling failure (I35)
 - * Security patch versioning failure (I36)
- Communication:
 - * UDP library configuration failure (I37)
 - * TCP library configuration failure (I38)
 - * Two-Phase Commit (TOC) error (I39)

Method

- Technique: Data handling failure (M01)
- Training Predictive Models:
 - Overfitting failure (M02)
 - Underfitting failure (M03)

- Incorrect parameter selection (M04)
- Coding a Blockchain Network:
 - Security mechanism failure (M05)
 - Scalability handling failure (M06)
- Public: Consensus mechanism failure (M07)
- Private: Permission mechanism failure (M08)
- Consortium: Interoperability mechanism failure (M09)
- Implementing an AI Algorithm:
 - Hyperparameter tuning failure (M10)
 - Low algorithm performance (M11)
- Validation:
 - Incorrect understanding of requirements (M12)
 - Lack of communication and collaboration between the team and the client (M13)
- Client Data Requirement:
 - Data unavailability due to privacy concerns (M14)
 - Inaccurate client data (M15)
- System Deployment:
 - Low build performance (M16)
 - Driver update failure (M17)